

REPOPSI Mid-Term Project Report

Project Title

TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs

Project Duration

October 2022 – July 2023 (nine months)

Report Submission

The mid-term report was submitted on March 31, 2023 via the EOSC Future Funding platform using the provided template.

About the Project

[REPOPSI](#) is an open digital repository for Open Access psychological scales, tests, and other research instruments translated into Serbian or developed by Serbian scientists.

More about the REPOPSI improvement project can be found at:

[EOSC Future grant: REPOPSI](#) on the RDA website

[How did we get to REPOPSI 2.0? The project that improved the Repository in a nutshell](#) on the REPOPSI website

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This report was created as part of the project titled "TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs", which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017536. The project has received support from the [EOSC Future](#) through the [RDA Open Call mechanism](#), based on evaluations of external, independent experts.

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1. Short description of the project progress

Short description of the project progress (including milestones/tasks completed). (300 words max.) *

- We assessed the Repository's TRUSTworthiness and FAIRness at the start of the project using two RDA outputs (CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025; FAIR Data Maturity Model) - the reports in English are available open-access at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535024> and at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535053>.
- We built the Repository website, available in English and Serbian, at <https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>.
- We developed an online survey form, available in English and Serbian, that the users will be able to fill in to submit their original psychological instruments or instrument translations/adaptations to the Repository.
- We developed a web application - created using the Shiny package for the R programming environment - that automates the search of the Repository's data and metadata; the web app is publicly available in English at <https://repopsi.shinyapps.io/repopsi/>.
- We recruited and trained three psychology master's students who will search published research materials in order to find and deposit new psychological instruments into the Repository. The training materials are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7789062>. Student assistants have so far searched more than 100 psychology doctoral theses and we held regular monthly meetings with them.
- We attended the RDA's 20th Plenary.
- We have been promoting the project via our institution's social media accounts and held regular online team meetings at least once a month.

2. Achievements

What have been the main achievements so far? What are the benefits of your project to the discipline communities and other project stakeholders? What are the planned concrete outcomes of your project? Have they evolved from the initial plan? (750 words max.) *

The first half of the project has focused on building Repository's technologies to achieve increased user-friendliness, as well as increased sustainability and findability. Following the development of the website, online contribution form, and search-and-download web application, the Repository has become more beneficial to its target user community (i.e., researchers, educators, students in psychology and other social sciences, clinical practitioners).

The new Repository website (available in both English and Serbian at <https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>) ensures that important information such as the Repository scope and terms of use are more transparently declared and more easily accessed by the users.

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We developed an online survey form, available in both English and Serbian, for the users to fill in to submit their original psychological instruments or instrument translations/adaptations to the Repository. This new form makes the contribution procedure more efficient, leaving less room for omissions and errors on the users' part. The form is currently available at <https://www.soscisurvey.de/repopsi/?act=2nFZGLaxl8r89QVki9iQOwOY> and will be embedded on the new website at <https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-contribute-to-repopsi/>.

We had professionals build a search-and-download web application, using the Shiny package for the R programming environment. The web app - publicly available in English at <https://repopsi.shinyapps.io/repopsi/> - improves the findability and discoverability of Repository's data and metadata, while providing the users with an additional and a more efficient way to search the Repository.

Another project achievement is the recruitment and training of three psychology master's students from the University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy (the training materials are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7789062>). The integration of more junior members into our team achieves an additional project goal - namely, raising the awareness of the importance of opening research data and of the best practices to do it. The student assistants have so far searched more than 100 psychology doctoral theses using the E-theses repository (<https://eteze.bg.ac.rs/>), identifying more than 300 potentially relevant psychological instruments. While not initially planned, the spreadsheet in which the student assistants have documented the instruments will be made openly available by the end of the project, as we have come to realise that it can constitute a valuable resource to the community on its own.

Apart from including more junior team members, our project also fosters the cross/multi-disciplinary approach by including a librarian, in addition to four project members who are psychology researchers (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/repopsi>).

3. Challenges

Describe the particular scientific, technical, research or business challenges that you have faced. Describe possible deviations from the initial project plans. (300 words max.) *

While the search-and-download web-app has been built and is publicly available at <https://repopsi.shinyapps.io/repopsi/>, we are still using the free shinyapps.io plan to host it. We will be able to upgrade it only once we have received the remaining grant instalments. This means that, until then, we will not be promoting it to the wider community, as the free plan cannot support enough user hours and, most of the time, it cannot support multiple users at once.

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Since the initial conceptualization of this project, the CoreTrustSeal have issued the new version of the requirements (CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements v01.00 2023-2025). This required us to invest more time into familiarising ourselves with the new guidelines. We, therefore, decided that the start-project Repository assessment using this resource consisted only of us indicating the compliance level for each of the Requirements (the report is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535053>). We will provide the guidance text describing the response statements and evidence for each requirement for the end-project assessment of the Repository.

We have decided that requiring users to create a “Contributor Account” via the new Repository website so that they are allowed to access the “How to contribute to REPOPSI” page to send psychological instruments for the Repository is an unnecessary barrier for the users. Instead, we made the online contribution form freely accessible to everyone, with a security captcha test at the beginning to prevent spam responses. While the contribution form is finished (<https://www.soscisurvey.de/repopsi/?act=2nFZGLaxl8r89QVkl9iQ0wOY>), we will dedicate some more time to usability testing, before we promote it to the wider community and embed it as <https://www.soscisurvey.de/repopsi/> on the new website at <https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-contribute-to-repopsi/>.

4. EOSC Relevant Outputs

Summarise how your work so far is relevant in the RDA and EOSC context, e.g.: a. What RDA outputs have you leveraged? b. How is your work relevant in the EOSC or specific domain context? c. Have you shared data, combined it with other data and made it more visible by using the services of the EOSC portal? d. Are you integrating research data into existing data catalogues and subsequent integration into the EOSC portal? e. Are you using discipline-specific metadata standards? (750 words max.) *

We leveraged two RDA outputs to assess the Repository’s TRUSTworthiness and FAIRness at the start of the project. Firstly, we used the CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements v01.00 2023-2025 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051011>) to assess the organisational infrastructure, digital object management, and technology of the Repository. Secondly, we used the “FAIR Data Maturity Model: Specification and Guidelines (1.0)” document (<https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>) developed by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group to assess the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of the Repository’s data and metadata. Our assessment reports in English are available open-access at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535024> and at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535053>. This way, our project has demonstrated how RDA standards/recommendations can be leveraged to improve the FAIRness and TRUSTworthiness of a community-led open digital repository for psychological research instruments.

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The project task of piloting the application of a controlled vocabulary to the Repository is ongoing. We have presented our work so far at the RDA/EOSC Future satellite event “Building blocks of Global Research Commons: Europe and beyond” (20 March 2023), which was part of RDA’s 20th Plenary in Gothenburg, Sweden (event programme is available at <https://www.rd-alliance.org/save-date-global-research-commons-europe-and-beyond>). We took part in the session “The glue to a successful Commons: Interoperability” and gave one of the lightning talks showcasing the RDA/EOSC Future community work. The slides of the talk are available open-access at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7787007>. As part of this project milestone, we plan to generate an XML file for each instrument in the Repository using the DataCite Metadata Schema (<https://schema.datacite.org/>), with embedded keywords taken from an existing FAIR-compliant thesaurus (such as the Library of Congress Subject Headings; <https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.d31795>) and other metadata (such as the licence information). This project activity so far highlights the issues that arise when attempting to make an open repository hosted on the free Open Science Framework platform (<https://osf.io/>) more interoperable (specifically, when attempting to make its metadata more machine-readable), while outlining specific data-support infrastructure needs. This project activity so far has also highlighted the need for a more detailed psychology-specific metadata thesaurus that is compliant with the FAIR principles.

5. Outreach activities/events

Please provide a list of outreach activities/events. Are there resources produced that can be reused? Please provide links. (No word limit.) *

We promoted the project outputs on social media in both English and Serbian:

- Grant award announcement
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/lira-lab-bgd_repopsi-openscience-openaccess-activity-7011683708596293632-VQ6t ;
https://twitter.com/LiraLab_Bgd/status/1605922850279489537 ;
<https://www.facebook.com/LiraLab.Bgd/posts/pfbid02UfFr2HgVFcknRbktrbPcX5NHGKLGJkrf8SJ79U1RDXdpg3Fk1xPmWeAcuXHTbf8Kl> ;
<https://mastodon.social/@alelazic/109557759830204611>
- Promoting the REPOPSI Start-Project Evaluation Using the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Report
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/alelazic_repopsi-fairdata-openscience-activity-7023342772438847488-Kgtg ; <https://twitter.com/AleLazic/status/1617585893501542402> ;
<https://mastodon.social/@alelazic/109739937037477955>

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We introduced the project as part of an invited presentation given at the Open Science Days IV, 3-4 November, 2022, Belgrade (Serbia) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7425349> ; <https://open.ac.rs/index.php/osd2022>

We gave a lightning talk for the RDA/EOSC Future Satellite Event "Building blocks of Global Research Commons: Europe and beyond" at the Research Data Alliance 20th Plenary Meeting <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7787007> ; <https://www.rd-alliance.org/save-date-global-research-commons-europe-and-beyond> ; https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=W_-lAbq2Qvg

We set up the REPOPSI project Zenodo community <https://zenodo.org/communities/repopsi-rda/>

We launched the Repository website <https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>

6. RDA Plenary in March 2023

How will you contribute to the RDA Plenary in March 2023? (200 words max.) *

Four members of the project team attended the RDA Plenary in March 2023. Aleksandra Lazić gave a lightning talk and participated in the discussion at the "The glue to a successful Commons: Interoperability" session, which was part of the RDA/EOSC Future satellite event "Building blocks of Global Research Commons: Europe and beyond" (event programme is available at <https://www.rd-alliance.org/save-date-global-research-commons-europe-and-beyond>). The title of the talk is "Interoperability and FAIR in disciplinary repositories using RDA's TRUST principles, based on the RDA grant to REPOPSI" The slides of the talk are available open-access at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7787007>, and the recording of the talk is available at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=W_-lAbq2Qvg. The talk was about our ongoing project task of piloting the application of a controlled vocabulary to the Repository. The talk highlighted the issues that arise when attempting to make an open repository hosted on the free Open Science Framework platform more interoperable (specifically, when attempting to make its metadata more machine-readable), while outlining specific data-support infrastructure needs. It also highlighted the need for a more detailed psychology-specific metadata thesaurus that is compliant with the FAIR principles.

7. Next steps

What have you planned next? (200 words max.) *

We will promote the new Repository website after we have (a) user tested the online instrument contribution form and embedded it on the "How to contribute to REPOPSI" page; (b) paid for the

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upgraded shinyapps.io plan to host the search-and-download web application and embedded the application on the “How to search REPOPSI” page; and (c) published a blog post introducing the funded project on the “Blog” page. We will hire the experts who built the search-and-download web application to hold a training session for the team on its maintenance. We will continue piloting the application of a controlled vocabulary to the Repository. We will start preparing the documentation needed to apply for the CoreTrust Seal certification; this documentation will also be part of the end-project Repository self-assessment. We will organise a local online workshop to share lessons learned. We will add the Repository as a new database entry in the FAIRsharing.org Registry. Student assistants will continue searching for psychological instruments and will start contacting instrument authors, as needed, and filling out contribution forms for the retrieved instruments that can be made open in the Repository.

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